

STUDIES IN SULPHONES. PART IV. SOME SUBSTITUTED ALKYL-ARYL AND DI-ARYL SULPHONES*

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By reacting sodium *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphinate with various alkyl halides, monochloroacetone, picryl chloride, *p*-nitrobenzyl bromide, ethylene chlorhydrin, benzoquinone and thymoquinone, the corresponding unsymmetrical sulphones have been synthesised. The action of diethyl bromomalonate and dicyandiamide on 4-nitro-4'-aminodiphenylsulphone has also been studied.

In continuation of our studies in sulphones (Jain, Iyer and Guha, *Science & Culture*, 1945, 11, 587, 568) we have now synthesised twenty new compounds detailed below.

By reacting the sodium salt of *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphinnic acid ("Organic Synthesis", Coll. vol. I, p. 8) with propyl, butyl, *iso*amyl and heptyl halides as also with monochloroacetone and picryl chloride, the respective *p*-acetaminophenyl alkyl sulphones (I), (III), (V), (VII), (IX) and (XI) were obtained. They were hydrolysed with hydrochloric acid to the corresponding *p*-aminophenyl alkyl sulphones (II), (IV), (VI), (VIII), (X) and (XII) respectively. Walker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 630) has prepared (IX) and reported its melting point as 91-92°, whereas our observed m. p. is 115°. We have repeated Walker's experiment and observed that the pure product actually melts at 115° which is the same as recorded by Sikdar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 203) whose paper came to our notice after we completed the work.

p-Acetaminophenyl- β -hydroxyethylsulphone (XIII) has been prepared by the action of ethylene chlorhydrin on sodium *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphinate. This could not be hydrolysed to the corresponding amino derivative owing to cleavage of the molecule on treatment with acid.

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By reacting sodium *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphinate with benzoquinone and thymoquinone according to the method of Hinsberg (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 3259; 1895, 28, 1315) the acetyl compounds (XIV), (XV) and the corresponding hydrolysed products (XV) and (XVII) are obtained.

After we had completed the work, we saw the paper on "The reaction between aromatic sulphinic acids and quinones and quinoneimines" by Pickolz (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 685) which reached us on 27th October, 1946. While Pickolz also has obtained products (XIV) and (XV), he has reported (contrary to our experience and Hinsberg's claim) that the reaction with thymoquinone could not be effected.

p-Acetaminophenyl-*p*'-nitrobenzylsulphone (XVIII) has been prepared by the action of *p*-nitrobenzyl bromide on sodium *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphinate. The product decomposes on hydrolysis.

By the action of diethyl bromomalonate on 4-amino-4'-nitrodiphenylsulphone, 4-dicarbethoxymethylamino-4'-nitrodiphenylsulphone (XIX) is obtained. Attempts to hydrolyse, reduce or condense the product with urea led to its cleavage. It is of interest to record that when sodium *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphinate is reacted with diethyl bromomalonate, a high melting product, insoluble in all solvents, and yielding sulphanic acid as a cleavage product on treatment with dilute sodium hydroxide in the cold, results.

When the hydrochloride of 4-amino-4'-nitrodiphenylsulphone is fused with dicyandiamide, 4-bignanyl-4'-nitrodiphenylsulphone (XX) results.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Preparation of Acetaminosulphones.—Sulphones (I), (III), (V), (VII), (IX) and (XI) were prepared by reacting *p*-acetaminobenzene sodium sulphinate with excess of the respective halogen compound in presence of alcohol. While in the reaction leading to the formation of sulphone (XIII) no solvent was used, isoamyl alcohol was employed for preparing sulphone (XVIII). The general procedure is as follows.

4-Acetaminophenylpropylsulphone (I).—*p*-Acetaminobenzene sodium sulphinate (9 g.), propyl iodide (8 g., excess) and alcohol (20 c. c.) were heated under reflux for 20 hours. Excess of the halide was then removed by steam and the resulting solid collected, washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 135°, yield 10.5 g. It is soluble in ethyl acetate, pyridine and acetic acid.

Sulphones (XIV) and (XVI) were prepared from benzoquinone and thymoquinone respectively, according to details given under (XIV).

4-Acetaminophenyl-2' : 5'-dihydroxyphenylsulphone (XIV).—Benzoquinone (2.16 g.) was added in small quantities to a boiling solution of *p*-acetaminobenzene sodium sulphinate (4 g.) in water (100 c. c.) and the heating continued for 15 minutes when the colour of the quinone was discharged and a pink precipitate resulted. After cooling, this was collected, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 271-72°, yield 5.2 g.

Hydrolysis of Acetaminosulphones.—Sulphones (II), (IV), (VI), (VIII), (X), (XII), (XV) and (XVII) were obtained by hydrolysing the corresponding acetaminosulphone with 5*N*-HCl as detailed under (II).

4-Aminophenylpropylsulphone (II).—Sulphone (I, 5 g.) was refluxed with 5*N*-HCl (50 c. c.) for 2 hours and the solution was cooled and neutralised with ammonia. The resulting precipitate was collected, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 99-100°, yield 3.8 g.

Sulphones (XIX) and (XX): *4-Nitrophenyl-4'-dicarboethoxymethylaminophenylsulphone* (XIX).—4-Nitro-4'-aminodiphenylsulphone (7 g.), diethyl bromomalonate (6 g.) and alcohol (20 c. c.) were heated under reflux on a water-bath for 16 hours. Alcohol was then removed by distillation under vacuum and the residue, on treatment with benzene, gave a precipitate. This was collected, washed with benzene and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 145° (decomp.), yield 7.5 g. It is soluble in alcohol, pyridine and acetic acid; insoluble in water, ether and benzene. On hydrolysis with HCl 4-nitro-4'-aminodiphenylsulphone was obtained.

4-Nitrophenyl-4'-biguanylphenylsulphone (XX).—Hydrochloride of 4-nitro-4'-aminodiphenylsulphone (15.8 g.) and dicyandiamide (8.4 g.) were heated together in an oil-bath at 150° for 10 hours. On cooling, it was leached with ammonium hydroxide and filtered. The product was freed from the reactants by successively boiling with water and alcohol. Being insoluble in all the common organic solvents it could not be crystallised. It decomposed above 300°, yield 8.8 g.

Melting points and analytical data of the compounds are tabulated below.

TABLE I

'Act' denotes acetaminophenyl ; 'Am.' aminophenyl and 'S', sulphone.

No.	Compound.	M. p.	Formula.	Nitrogen per cent	
				Found.	Calc.
I.	4-act. propyl-S.	135°	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ O ₂ NS	6.66	5.80
II.	4-Am. propyl-S.	99°	C ₉ H ₁₃ O ₂ NS	7.00	7.04
III.	4-Act. butyl-S.	112°	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ NS	5.48	5.50
IV.	4-Am. butyl-S.	98°	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O ₂ NS	6.76	6.60
V.	4-Act. isoamyl-S.	108°	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ NS	5.32	5.18
VI.	4-Am. isoamyl-S.	114°	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ O ₂ NS	5.97	6.14
VII.	4-Act. heptyl-S.	99°	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ O ₂ NS	4.63	4.71
VIII.	4-Am. heptyl-S.	97°	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ NS	5.56	5.50
IX.	4-Act. acetonyl-S.	115°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₄ NS	5.56	5.50
X.	4-Am. acetonyl-S.	135°	C ₉ H ₁₁ O ₃ NS	6.71	6.57
XI.	4-Act. picryl-S.	240° (decomp.)	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₃ S	13.72	13.66
XII.	4-Am. picryl-S.	165° (decomp.)	C ₁₂ H ₈ O ₃ N ₃ S	15.10	15.21
XIII.	4-Act. β-hydroxyethyl-S.	165° (decomp.)	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₃ NS	5.81	5.75
XIV.	4-Act. 2' : 5'-dihydroxyphenyl-S.	272°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ NS	4.50	4.60
XV.	4-Am. 2' : 5'-dihydroxyphenyl-S.	177°	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₃ NS	5.18	5.28
XVI.	4-Act. 2' : 5'-dihydroxy-3'-isopropyl-6'-methylphenyl-S.	244°	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ O ₃ NS	3.79	3.86
XVII.	4-Am. 2' : 5'-dihydroxy-3'-isopropyl-6'-methylphenyl-S.	234°	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ O ₃ NS	4.29	4.36
XVIII.	4-Act. 4'-nitrobenzyl-S.	270° (decomp.)	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₂ S	8.13	8.33
XIX.	4-Nitrophenyl-4'-dicarbethoxymethyl-Am-S.	145° (decomp.)	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₂ S	6.4	6.43
XX.	4-Nitrophenyl-4'-biguanylphenyl-S.	300° (decomp.)	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₆ S	23.18	23.22

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